

National Cancer Institute, Comprehensive Partnerships to Advance Cancer Health Equity (CPACHE): U54 Outreach Evaluation Toolkit

Developed by the Outreach Special Interest Group (SIG)

Name	CPACHE Affiliation	U54 Grant Numbers
Fred Snyder	National Institutes of Health (NIH) National Cancer Institute (Contractor)	Senior Evaluation Researcher, NCI
Kelly Laurila	University of Arizona Cancer Center (UACC) Northern Arizona University (NAU)	UACC U54CA143924 NAU U54CA143925
Linda Behar-Horenstein	University of FL Florida A&M University (FAMU) University of Southern California Norris CC	UF U54CA233444 FAMU U54CA233396 USC U54CA233465
Sarah Suiter	Vanderbilt Ingram Cancer Center Meharry Medical College Tennessee State University	VICC U54CA163072 MMC U54CA163069 TSU U54CA163066
Kevin Cassel	University of Hawaii Cancer Center UOH) University of Guam (UOG)	UoH U54CA143727 UoG U54CA143728
Tanya Elisa Penn & Anthony Barrios	San Diego State University University of California San Diego	SDSU U54CA132384 UCSD U54CA132379
Jessica McIntyre & Giselle Tolentino	Ponce Health Sciences University Moffitt Cancer Center Partnership	PHSU U54CA163071 MCC U54CA163068
Kimberly Harris	North Carolina Central University University North Carolina (UNC), Linebarger	NCCU U54CA156735 UNC U54CA156733

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CPACHE U54 Outreach Evaluation Toolkit

Purpose: The Outreach Toolkit was developed to provide standardized metrics and measures for the U54 CPACHE centers to: (1) foster data integration, standardization of data elements, data interoperability and to enhance the quality of evaluation reporting to NCI; (2) promote a robust understanding of how funding benefits trainees, Early-Stage Investigators (ESI), community locales, patient advocates, and others that are served; and (3) enable comparative inquiries across centers.

Background: CPACHE Partnership institutions (PAR-18-361) are expected to: 1) increase the cancer research and cancer research education capacity of the institutions serving underserved health disparity populations and underrepresented students (ISUPS); 2) increase the number of students and investigators from underrepresented populations engaged in cancer research; 3) improve the effectiveness of cancer centers (CC) in developing and sustaining research programs focused on cancer health disparities and increase the number of investigators and students conducting cancer health disparities research; and 4) develop and implement cancer-related activities that benefit the surrounding underserved communities. A group of CPACHE Evaluators organized to form U54 CPACHE Outreach Evaluation Special Interest Group (SIG). The SIG agreed to focus on the CPACHE program goal 4 above. The SIG used previously developed CPACHE site-specific evaluation matrices (with site-specific process and impact measures) as the foundation to identify common evaluation constructs across sites. The SIG then used a consensus building process to identify evaluation constructs, definitions and specific instruments designed to measure those constructs related to community outreach and engagement with a focus on reducing cancer-related health disparities among underserved populations.

This document contains separate and distinct work products that complement the **U54 CPACHE Evaluation Matrix** developed by McIntyre J, Peral S, Dodd SJ, Behar-Horenstein L, Madanat H, Shain A, DeJesus S, Laurila K, Robinett H, Holmes K, Aguila N, Marzan M, Sychala L, Barrios A, Rivers D, Loest H, Drennan M, Suiter S, Richey J, Brown T, Webb L, Hubbard K, Scarinci IC. Abstract D041: Efforts to implement a participatory evaluation plan for Comprehensive Partnerships to Advance Cancer Health Equity. *Cancer Epidemiology, Biomarkers & Prevention*. Published June 2020. <https://doi.org/10.1158/1538-7755.DISP19-D041>

CPACHE Common Evaluation Metrics:

Standardized measures enhance the possibility of conducting multi-site studies across CPACHE initiatives. The use of these evaluation instruments is not required but represents an opportunity to increase the power of our findings, conduct psychometric evaluations of instruments, and enable to compare across sites. The NCI continues to encourage the use of site-specific constructs in addition to adopting common metrics and measures.

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Directions for the Use of the Toolkit:

Each U54 CPACHE may choose to use any of the suggested variables, related items, and indicators with the proviso that proper attribution is expressly given to the U54 CPACHE Outreach Special Interest Group.

If a site is interested in a cross-site evaluation research study, please consult the respective Human Subject's Review Boards (for each institution) to obtain the appropriate approvals or documentation that the study is not considered human subject research.

Please review the suggested question format and consider those recommendations in your survey design (in Redcap or Qualtrics etc.) to ascertain, for example, if multiple responses are allowed. This will aid greater uniformity in data collection across sites, increase the capacity for national comparative/multi-site projects, and enhance the integrity of CPACHE program evaluation.

Adapting Instruments for your CPACHE:

Researchers who wish to adapt the variables and indicators within this document are asked to seek written permission from the first and second author prior to use. CPACHE Centers may wish to change the references to U54 and/or CPACHE and insert your partnership's new name instead.

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Summary: Evaluation Constructs and Definitions

Evaluation Construct	Definition
Demographic and population characteristics	Identification of the population (community members or members of community organizations) engaged.
Cancer priorities	Identification of cancer priorities and needs.
Cancer related policy development	Fidelity of written vs enacted cancer policy.
Cancer related policy implementation	Intended or unintended consequences (positive/negative) of policy implementation.
Cancer knowledge and awareness (pre/post)	Change in participant familiarity with cancer types, risks, prevention, screening, caretakers, quality of life, precision medicine, clinical trials, or bio-banking etc.
Investigator knowledge or skills and engagement	Changes in investigator knowledge or skills regarding culturally responsive community engagement or patient practices in research and effective strategies for disseminating results to lay audiences. Changes in investigator outreach practice.
Access to cancer data	Population's ability to access information and utilization of cancer data for decision making.
Cancer clinical trials	Awareness of cancer related trials
Biospecimen donations	Education about biospecimen donations.
Dissemination of research findings to communities	Sharing research findings with community in a culturally responsive manner.
Community engagement	Bi-directional communication in cancer research topic identification, shared decision making and trust building and new partnership development.
Community capacity building	Fostering community contributions to cancer-related research, outreach or cancer programming, and negotiating IRB/data ownership and return on investment (ROI).

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Demographic and Population Characteristics	
Definition	Identification of the population (community members or members of community organizations) engaged.
Intended respondents	The focus of this evaluation is on recipients of CPACHE efforts. This tool is not intended to serve as a stand-alone instrument. These demographic questions should be included whenever you are surveying community members so as to understand potential racial/ethnic, age, gender, etc. differences in knowledge, awareness and behaviors.
Suggested periodicity	Dependent on individual site activities
Other notes for users	Partnerships may also want to include information about the roles (i.e., Community Health Educator) of individuals conducting outreach work.

1. **Are you of Hispanic or Latinx origin?** *(A person of Cuban, Mexican, Puerto Rican, South or Central American, or other Spanish culture or origin regardless of race)?*
 - a. Yes
 - b. No
 - c. I choose not to self-identify

2. **What is your race?** *Select all that apply.*
 - a. American Indian/Alaska Native
 - b. Asian
 - c. Black/African American
 - d. Native Hawaiian/Other Pacific Islander
 - e. White
 - f. I choose not to self-identify

CPACHE sites may opt to include other relevant categories (may vary regionally).

3. **Gender**
 - a. Male
 - b. Female
 - c. Prefer to self-identify (open-ended response)
 - d. Prefer to not respond

4. **Age**
 - a. Under 18
 - b. 18-24 years old

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- c. 25-34 years old
- d. 35-44 years old
- e. 45-54 years old
- f. 55-64 years old
- g. 65-74 years old
- h. 75 or older

5. What is your preferred language?

- a. English
- b. Spanish
- c. Chinese (Mandarin or Cantonese)
- d. Other: _____
- e. *CPACHE sites may opt to include other relevant categories (may vary regionally).*

6. Zipcode *(open-ended response)*

7. What type of health insurance or health care coverage do you currently have?

Select all that apply

- a. None, no insurance and without coverage at the present time
- b. Coverage provided through a current or former employer or labor union (excluding military coverage)
- c. Coverage through an individual plan
- d. Coverage through the military (e.g., CHAMPUS, Tri-Care)
- e. Coverage through the Indian Health Services
- f. Coverage through Medicare
- g. Coverage through Medicaid
- h. Other, specify:

8. What is your total family income?

- a. Less than \$25,000
- b. \$25,000 - \$49,999
- c. \$50,000 - \$74,999
- d. \$75,000 - \$99,999
- e. \$100,000 or more

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Cancer Priorities (Instrument)	
Definition	Identification of cancer priorities and needs.
Intended respondents	Outreach Core and the Planning and Evaluation Core leads or Principal Investigators (One submission per CPACHE program)
Suggested periodicity	To be determined by each CPACHE based on changing needs
Other notes for users	We recommend that the Executive team discusses the responses together and reaches consensus before completing this survey.

1. How are your CPACHE program's cancer priorities set? This includes research interests among community partners. *You may select more than one response.*

- a. Community or Community Advisory Board engagement
- b. Comprehensive Cancer Center catchment area needs
- c. CPACHE Program (Executive leadership team)
- d. National Cancer Institute priorities
- e. A collaborative process (bi-directional) *(Please specify collaborator groups or organizations.)*
- f. Other (Specify) _____

2. What type of data are utilized to set cancer research priorities? *You may select more than one response.*

- a. Incidence
- b. Mortality
- c. Prevalence
- d. Surveillance
- e. Social determinants of health
- f. Unsure
- g. Other (Specify) _____

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Cancer Related Policy Development (Instrument)	
Definition	Fidelity of written vs enacted cancer policy.
Intended respondents	CPACHE funded project investigators, core leads, or PIs
Suggested periodicity	Annually
Other notes for users	Process oriented

1. **Respondent CPACHE Roles(s)** *Select all that apply*
 - a. Funded project co-lead (CPACHE pre-pilot, pilot, or full project)
 - b. Administrative Core PI/lead
 - c. Outreach Core PI/lead
 - d. Research Education Core PI/lead
 - e. Planning and Evaluation Core PI/lead
 - f. Other *(please specify your CPACHE role)* _____

2. **Please describe any policy or practice (organizational, institutional, or clinical practice, local, state, federal, tribal, etc.) related changes that you have engaged in as a result of your work with the U54.** *(open-ended question)*

Respond (yes/no) to the following items and consider each of these activities in terms of policy development that might lead to changes in policy or practice (organizational, institutional, or clinical practice, local, state, federal, tribal etc.)

3. **Have you developed print or media materials that explain to others who are at risk for *(specify relevant types of cancer)* cancer where they can get screened?**
Yes/No *If yes, please provide specific examples for each type.*

4. **Have you engaged in activities to increase funding for cancer education in your local community?**
Yes/No *If yes, please provide specific types and examples.*

5. **Have you engaged in activities to increase cancer research funding?**
Yes/No *If yes, please provide specific types and examples.*

6. **Have you engaged in activities to improve access to cancer screening?**
Yes/No *If yes, please provide specific types and examples.*

7. **Have you engaged in activities to improve access to cancer treatment?**
Yes/No *If yes, please provide specific examples.*

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Cancer Related Policy Implementation (Instrument)	
Definition	Intended or unintended consequences (positive and/or negative) of policy implementation.
Intended respondents	CPACHE funded project investigators, core leads, or PIs
Suggested periodicity	Annually
Other notes for users	Changes in policies, or practices pertaining to clinical or research practice. Changes may occur at an institutional, organizational, local, state, tribal, or federal level.

1. **Respondent CPACHE Roles(s)** *Select all that apply*
 - a. Funded project co-lead (CPACHE pre-pilot, pilot, or full project)
 - b. Administrative Core PI/lead
 - c. Outreach Core PI/lead
 - d. Research Education Core PI/lead
 - e. Planning and Evaluation Core PI/lead
 - f. Other *(please specify your CPACHE role)* _____

2. **Have existing policies or practices changed as a result of the work with the U54?**
 - a. Yes
 - b. No

3. **If yes (Q2), please describe any changes that have occurred** *(open-ended)*
Consider the following types of changes: institutional, organizational, local, state, tribal, or federal level etc.

4. **What entities, groups, or institutions were involved in the change?** *(open-ended)*

5. **What was the specific policy or practice?** *(open-ended)*

6. **What actions or steps were taken to implement the policy or practice?** *(open-ended)*

7. **How have those enacted policies or practices impacted cancer health disparities?** *(open-ended)*

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Cancer Knowledge and Awareness (Pre-Instrument)	
Definition	Baseline participant familiarity with cancer types, risks, prevention, screening, caretakers, quality of life, precision medicine, clinical trials, or bio-banking etc.
Intended respondents	Community members in the catchment area who are engaged.
Suggested periodicity	Site specific
Other notes for users	<p>We suggest including relevant demographic and population characteristic questions to assess subgroup comparisons.</p> <p>Several additional NCI-authored pre/post knowledge tools are available in Appendix B: Supplemental Materials.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clinical Trials knowledge (being tested via NCI’s National Outreach Network (NON)) • HPV knowledge (being tested via NON) • Colorectal Cancer (CRC) knowledge (validated via NON)

1. Cancer knowledge self-assessment

Cancer knowledge (self-assessment questions)	Yes	No	Not applicable
I can now explain, in my own words, what <i>(specific type)</i> cancer is.	Yes	No	N/A
I can state the risks associated with <i>(specific type)</i> cancer.	Yes	No	N/A
I can describe the treatments for <i>(specific type)</i> cancer.	Yes	No	N/A
I can identify the symptoms of <i>(specific type)</i> cancer that are present during the early stages.	Yes	No	N/A
I can identify the symptoms of <i>(specific type)</i> cancer that are present during the latter stages.	Yes	No	N/A
I know when to go to get screened for <i>(specific type)</i> cancer.	Yes	No	N/A
I can identify the symptoms of <i>(specific type)</i> cancer that place <i>(population)</i> at most risk for developing this disease.	Yes	No	N/A
I can explain to others why it is important to get screened for <i>(specific type)</i> cancer.	Yes	No	N/A
I can explain to others where to seek treatment for their <i>(specific type)</i> cancer.	Yes	No	N/A

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Cancer Knowledge and Awareness (Post-Instrument)	
Definition	Change in participant familiarity with cancer types, risks, prevention, screening, caretakers, quality of life, precision medicine, clinical trials, or bio-banking etc.
Intended respondents	Community members in the catchment area who are engaged.
Suggested periodicity	Site specific
Other notes for users	<p>We suggest including relevant demographic and population characteristic questions to assess subgroup comparisons.</p> <p>Several additional NCI-authored pre/post knowledge tools are available in Appendix B: Supplemental Materials.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clinical Trials knowledge (being tested via NCI’s National Outreach Network (NON)) • HPV knowledge (being tested via NON) • Colorectal Cancer (CRC) knowledge (validated via NON)

1. Cancer knowledge self-assessment

Cancer knowledge (self-assessment questions)	Yes	No	Not applicable
I can now explain, in my own words, what <i>(specific type)</i> cancer is.	Yes	No	N/A
I can state the risks associated with <i>(specific type)</i> cancer.	Yes	No	N/A
I can describe the treatments for <i>(specific type)</i> cancer.	Yes	No	N/A
I can identify the symptoms of <i>(specific type)</i> cancer that are present during the early stages.	Yes	No	N/A
I can identify the symptoms of <i>(specific type)</i> cancer that are present during the latter stages.	Yes	No	N/A
I know when to go to get screened for <i>(specific type)</i> cancer.	Yes	No	N/A
I can identify the symptoms of <i>(specific type)</i> cancer that place <i>(population)</i> at most risk for developing this disease.	Yes	No	N/A
I can explain to others why it is important to get screened for <i>(specific type)</i> cancer.	Yes	No	N/A
I can explain to others where to seek treatment for their <i>(specific type)</i> cancer.	Yes	No	N/A

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Investigator knowledge or skills & engagement (Instrument)	
Definition	<p><u>Knowledge/skills</u>- Changes in investigator knowledge or skills regarding culturally responsive community engagement or patient practices in research and effective strategies for disseminating results to lay audiences.</p> <p><u>Engagement</u>- Changes in investigator outreach practices.</p>
Intended respondents	The Planning and Evaluation Core may decide which individuals receive this survey. Investigators (primarily CPACHE full/pilot co-leads) or the Outreach core may be the recipients.
Suggested periodicity	Annually
Other notes for users	Include these questions in funded investigators' progress or research productivity reports.

1. **Respondent CPACHE Roles(s)** *Select all that apply*
 - a. Funded project co-lead (CPACHE pre-pilot, pilot, or full project)
 - b. Administrative Core PI/lead
 - c. Outreach Core PI/lead
 - d. Research Education Core PI/lead
 - e. Planning and Evaluation Core PI/lead
 - f. Other *(please specify your CPACHE role)* _____

2. **As a result of your participation in the U54 CPACHE, describe ways that you have modified your engagement with the community or in-patient practice to ensure that approach is culturally responsive to lay persons. Please provide some examples.** *(Open-ended question)*

3. **As a result of your participation in the U54 CPACHE, describe ways that your outreach practices (community engagement, dissemination, etc.) have changed. Please provide some examples.** *(Open-ended)*

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Access to Cancer Data (Instrument)	
Definition	Population’s ability to access information about cancer data for decision making.
Intended respondents	Outreach team representative (one submission per site)
Suggested periodicity	Annually
Other notes for users	None

1. CPACHE site (institution) _____
2. Who is responsible to share or disseminate information about access to and utilization of cancer data?
 - a. Outreach team member (Community Health Educator etc.)
 - b. Pilot/Full project co-lead
 - c. Cancer center (not CPACHE responsibility)
 - d. Other external resources (non-CPACHE) please describe _____
 - e. Other (please identify role) _____

3. Please indicate by selecting Yes or No if your CPACHE center provides the following information to the groups shown below.

Note- these questions should be calibrated to be relevant to CPACHE cancer foci.

Types of information	Community member(s)	Investigator(s)	Service provider(s)
Cancer incidence/mortality data	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No
Services related to cancer prevention	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No
Screening, diagnosis, treatment resources	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No
Palliative or hospice care support services	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No
Other support services (survivorship etc.)	Yes/No	Yes/No	Yes/No

If you selected “other support services” in the question above, please describe *(open ended)*

4. What are the sources for the information being provided? *Please select all that apply.*
 - a. Research project findings (CPACHE pilot/full project outcomes)
 - b. SEER data/Cancer.gov (service resources/directories)
 - c. National Cancer Institute
 - d. Behavioral Risk Factor Surveillance System (BRFSS)
 - e. State cancer registry data
 - f. Other _____

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Cancer Clinical Trials (Instrument)	
Definition	Awareness of cancer related trials
Intended respondents	Outreach member facilitating the training
Suggested periodicity	Administer alongside training opportunities
Other notes for users	None

Clinical Trials Education

1. CPACHE site (institution) _____
2. Did you conduct clinical trial related education during this reporting period?
Reporting period should be defined by the site.
 - a. Yes
 - b. No
3. Please indicate which groups you reached during this reporting period (indicate reporting period) *Logic may be added for items 4-5 below depending on response*
 - c. Community
 - d. Health professionals
4. What methods/media channels were used to promote clinical trials participation in the community?
5. Educational Materials/Resources Used (*Choose all that apply*)
 - a. Print (Flyer, Newsletter, Brochure, Manual/Guide) Video/DVD
 - b. Digital media (web-based)
 - c. Mobile App
 - d. TV
 - e. Radio
 - f. Newspaper
 - g. Social Media (Facebook, YouTube, Twitter etc.)
 - h. Other _____
6. Type of Activity (*Choose all that apply*)
 - a. One on one
 - i. Estimate the total number of people reached: _____
 - b. Workshop
 - i. Estimate the total number of people reached: _____
 - c. Health Fair
 - i. Estimate the total number of people reached: _____

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- d. Conference
 - i. Estimate the total number of people reached: _____
 - e. Community Presentation
 - i. Estimate the total number of people reached: _____
 - f. Community Focus Group
 - i. Estimate the total number of people reached: _____
7. **Did you encourage your audience to access additional information about cancer clinical trials? Yes/No**
- a. **If yes, please specify**
8. **Were members of the audience from a rural area?**
- a. Yes
 - b. No
 - c. Unsure
9. **Were members of the audience from Hispanic or Latinx origin?** (*A person of Cuban, Mexican, Puerto Rican, South or Central American, or other Spanish culture or origin regardless of race*)?
- a. Yes
 - b. No
 - c. Unsure
10. **To the best of your knowledge, which of the following best describes your audience's racial background?** (*Check all that apply*)
- a. American Indian/Alaska Native
 - b. Asian
 - c. Black or African-American
 - d. Native Hawaiian/Other Pacific Islander
 - e. White
 - f. Unsure
- (CPACHE sites may opt to include other relevant categories (may vary regionally).)

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Biospecimen donations (Instrument)	
Definition	Education about biospecimen donations.
Intended respondents	Outreach team member/one per site
Suggested periodicity	Annual
Other notes for users	None

1. Is your CPACHE program providing education about biospecimens? Yes/No

2. What methods/media channels were used to provide education about biospecimens donations in the community?

A. Educational Materials/Resources Used *(Choose all that apply)*

- a. Print (Flyer, Newsletter, Brochure, Manual/Guide)
- b. Video/DVD
- c. Digital media (web-based)
- d. Mobile App
- e. TV
- f. Radio
- g. Newspaper
- h. Social Media (Facebook, YouTube, Twitter etc.)
- i. Other _____

B. Type of Activity *(Choose all that apply)*

- a. One on one
- b. Workshop
- c. Health Fair
- d. Conference
- e. Community Presentation
- f. Community Focus Group

3. Were members of the audience from a rural area?

- a. Yes
- b. No
- c. Unsure

4. Were members of the audience from Hispanic or Latinx origin? *(A person of Cuban, Mexican, Puerto Rican, South or Central American, or other Spanish culture or origin regardless of race)?*

- a. Yes
- b. No
- c. Unsure

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5. **To the best of your knowledge, which of the following best describes your audience's racial background?** *(Check all that apply)*

- a) American Indian/Alaska Native
- b) Asian
- c) Black or African-American
- d) Native Hawaiian/Other Pacific Islander
- e) White
- f) Unsure

CPACHE sites may opt to include other relevant categories (may vary regionally).

6. **Is the community engaged in the conversation about biospecimen ownership, use, and protections in your CPACHE program?**

- a. Yes
- b. No
- c. Unsure

If yes, please explain.

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Dissemination of research findings to communities (Instrument)	
Definition	Sharing research findings with community in a culturally responsive manner.
Intended respondents	Funded project investigators
Suggested periodicity	Twice a year
Other notes for users	Consider including these questions with other progress reports or surveys for funded project investigators.

1. **Please indicate project type:**
 - a. Full project
 - b. Pilot project

2. **Please list the project co-leads at the institutions serving underserved health disparity populations and underrepresented students (ISUPS) and Cancer Center.**
 - a. ISUPS Investigators (first/last names) _____
 - b. Cancer Center Investigators (first/last names) _____

3. **Research project title:** _____

4. **Explain how you disseminate your (pilot/full) research findings to communities in a culturally responsive manner. (*open-ended question*)**

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Community engagement (Instrument)	
Definition	Bi-directional communication in cancer research topic identification, shared decision making and trust building and new partnership development.
Intended respondents	Core PIs, funded project investigators, or MPIs
Suggested periodicity	Annually
Other notes for users	None

1. CPACHE partnership:

(Please name your specific CPACHE institution, do not use acronyms)

- a. Cancer Center (CC) _____
- b. Institution serving underserved health disparity populations and underrepresented students (ISUPS)

2. Please indicate the affiliation of the person responding to this questionnaire

- A. MPI (contact PI)
- B. Administrative Core
- C. Planning and Evaluation Core
- D. Outreach Core
- E. Research Education Core
- F. Funded project lead (pilot/full)
- G. Shared Resource (lead)
- H. Other (please describe) _____

3. Please indicate whether the individual selected in above represents the Cancer Center (CC) or institution serving underserved health disparity populations and underrepresented students (ISUPS)

- A. Cancer Center
- B. Institution serving underserved health disparity populations and underrepresented students (ISUPS)

4. *Survey logic- This question should only be asked if a respondent selects funded project lead (F). Please explain how you engage community partners at different stages in the research process and provide some examples. (open-ended question)*

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5. Please explain how you seek to ensure that there is shared decision making with your community partners or community advisory board. *Provide some examples.*
6. Please explain how you seek to ensure that there is trust building within your community. *Provide some examples.*
7. Please explain how you seek to ensure new partnership development with your community. *Provide some examples.*

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Community capacity building (Instrument)	
Definition	Foster community contributions to cancer-related research, outreach, or cancer programming, and negotiating IRB/data ownership and return on investment (ROI).
Intended respondents	Community advisory board members
Suggested periodicity	Annual
Other notes for users	This should be an anonymous survey. Use the recommended citation to acknowledge the teams that developed this instrument.

Citation- *Please include this citation when you use this instrument.*

The Community Advisory Board (CAB) survey was developed by Dr. Oscar Miller, Professor of Sociology at Tennessee State University, member of the CPACHE partnership between Meharry Medical College, Vanderbilt University, and Tennessee State University.

Items were adapted from:

- Andrews J, Newman S, Cox M, Meadows O. *Are We Ready? A toolkit for academic-community partnerships in preparation for community-based participatory research*. Charleston SC: Medical University of South Carolina, 2011.
- Jonathan M. Kagan, Scott R. Rosas, Rona L. Siskind³, Russell D. Campbell, Daniel Gondwe, David Munroe, William M. K. Trochim, and Jeffrey T. Schouten. *Community-Researcher Partnerships at NIAID HIV/AIDS Clinical Trials Sites: Insights for Evaluation & Enhancement*. Prog Community Health Partnership. 2012; 6(3): 311–320. doi:10.1353/cpr.2012.0034

1. Please indicate the role that best describes your interaction with the CAB:

- a. Community Advisory Board (CAB) Member
- b. CPACHE Team member (Core lead, PI, staff, or investigator)

2. Have you shared anything that you learned as a result of your participation in the CAB with your friends, family members, or neighbors? If so, please tell us a little about it.

3. What was the biggest benefit you gained from participating in the CAB?

4. Is there anything else you want us to know?

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5. Please suggest at least one way to improve the CAB.

The following items refer to the Community Advisory Board (CAB), the CPACHE partnership including the Cancer Center partner and institutions serving underserved health disparity populations and underrepresented students (ISUPS) institution(s), and groups affected by cancer disparities (Community).

6. Circle the number (1-5) that indicates the level of importance (from your perspective) and your level of agreement with each of the items below.

Importance	Agreement
1 = Not Important	1 = Strongly Disagree
2 = Somewhat Important	2 = Disagree
3 = Important	3 = Neither
4 = Very Important	4 = Agree
	5 = Strongly Agree

1. The number of CAB meetings is about right
2. CAB meeting times are accommodating
3. The CAB helps in planning studies conducted through the Partnership
4. The CAB helps guide implementation of studies conducted through the Partnership
5. CAB members nominate community members to the CAB
6. The CAB is informed about research goals
7. The CAB is informed about study benefits to the Community
8. The CAB helps produce culturally competent cancer information
9. The Partnership assesses CAB training needs
10. The Partnership provides needed training to CAB
11. CAB and Partnership staff learn from each other
12. CAB and Partnership staff show mutual respect
13. Research staff update the CAB about ongoing studies
14. Partnership informs public about cancer research
15. Partnership informs public about cancer prevention
16. Partnership informs public about cancer treatment
17. Research staff presentations give CAB enough information to provide practical feedback
18. The CAB helps to determine Community research priorities
19. The CAB contributes ideas to improve cancer outreach efforts

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20. The CAB is representative of the Community
21. CAB has a clear sense of purpose
22. CAB agendas are appropriate
23. CAB meetings include time for discussion, feedback, and comments
24. CAB process is worth my time
25. I am satisfied with the CAB
26. I would recommend the CAB to my colleagues

Appendix A: Supplemental Evaluation Materials

Items included in this appendix are suggested for use if they align with your CPACHE sites activities. Any items labeled “Tracking Template” can be adopted by sites to assist with data collection for aggregation.

Cancer Priorities: Supplemental Materials	
Definition	Identification of cancer priorities and needs.
Rationale for why these questions were removed from the main toolkit.	The SIG discussed whether sites are documenting cancer priority setting in grant reports, but not really evaluating that process. These questions emerged during an exploratory discussion while the SIG tried to understand whether sites are evaluating the priority setting process. Consider this item in the future for a conversations or panel discussion with the CPACHE evaluator group. These sub-questions were removed from the toolkit.

1. **Please respond to the questions below to address whether your CPACHE Evaluation team is measuring the process for setting cancer priorities.**
 - a. **Are you evaluating the cancer priority setting process?**
 - i. Yes/No
 - b. **Are you evaluating the outcomes associated with specific priorities?**
 - i. Yes/No
 - c. **Is your center adaptable to changing needs or priorities?**
 - i. Yes/No
 - ii. **If yes, why did they change (what caused them to change), how have they adapted (descriptive)? How is adaptability being measured and or tracked? (*Open-ended response*)**

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Community Capacity Building: Supplemental Materials	
Definition	Foster community contributions to cancer-related research, outreach or cancer programming, and negotiating IRB/data ownership and return on investment (ROI).
Intended respondents	Community advisory board members
Suggested periodicity	Annual
Other notes for users	This should be an anonymous survey. Please use the recommended citation to acknowledge the teams that developed this instrument.

1. Please indicate the degree to which to agree with the following statements.

Replace blue text with topic relevant to your programs outreach work

As a result of my participation in the CAB, I experienced...	<i>Please select one response per item</i>				
An increase in my knowledge of (XXX)	Strongly agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Not applicable
An increase in my knowledge of (XXX) cancer risk	Strongly agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Not applicable
An increase in my knowledge of (XXX) strategies	Strongly agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Not applicable
An increase in my ability to explain (XXX) to others	Strongly agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Not applicable
An increase in my ability to explain (XXX) risk to others	Strongly agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Not applicable
An increase in my ability to explain (XXX) strategies to others	Strongly agree	Agree	Disagree	Strongly disagree	Not applicable

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Clinical Trials Knowledge: Supplemental Materials (NCI)	
Intended respondents	Community members in the catchment area who are engaged.
Suggested periodicity	Administer alongside outreach activities.
Other notes for users	<i>This Instrument was developed by the NCI/CRCHD</i> Suggestion to include relevant demographic and population characteristic questions.

(Pre-Educational Activity)

Please answer each of the items below as True or False:

- | | | |
|---|-------------------------------|--------------------------------|
| 1) A clinical trial can test a new medicine or treatment to see if it is safe. | <input type="checkbox"/> True | <input type="checkbox"/> False |
| 2) In a clinical trial, a patient will always get the new medicine or treatment being tested. | <input type="checkbox"/> True | <input type="checkbox"/> False |
| 3) The consent form explains the known risks of being in the clinical trial. | <input type="checkbox"/> True | <input type="checkbox"/> False |
| 4) Once I sign a consent form, I must stay in the clinical trial until my doctor tells me I'm done. | <input type="checkbox"/> True | <input type="checkbox"/> False |
| 5) Clinical trials of new medicines or treatments are carefully reviewed for safety by a group of research experts and community members. | <input type="checkbox"/> True | <input type="checkbox"/> False |
| 6) Clinical trials test whether a new medicine or treatment works. | <input type="checkbox"/> True | <input type="checkbox"/> False |
| 7) Any medicine will have the same effect for all persons regardless of race or ethnicity. | <input type="checkbox"/> True | <input type="checkbox"/> False |
| 8) Clinical trials help decide which doses of a medicine are best. | <input type="checkbox"/> True | <input type="checkbox"/> False |
| 9) You can only join a clinical trial after you have tried all other options. | <input type="checkbox"/> True | <input type="checkbox"/> False |
| 10) One possible benefit of participating in a clinical trial is getting new and possibly better treatments. | <input type="checkbox"/> True | <input type="checkbox"/> False |
| 11) All the possible side effects of a new medicine being tested are known before the clinical trial starts. | <input type="checkbox"/> True | <input type="checkbox"/> False |

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Intentions

For each of the following statements, select the response choice that best applies to you.

Please tell us how strongly you agree or disagree with the following statements:	Strongly Agree	Agree	Unsure	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I am likely to seek out information regarding clinical trials.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I am likely to search for a clinical trial that I might be eligible for.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
It is important for persons who belong to minority groups (persons of color) to participate in clinical trials.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I would consider talking to my doctor or health care provider about clinical trials that are right for me.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I am likely to join a clinical trial.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I am likely to talk to family/friends about joining a clinical trial.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

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HPV Knowledge: Supplemental Materials (NCI)	
Intended respondents	Community members in the catchment area who are engaged.
Suggested periodicity	Administer alongside outreach activities.
Other notes for users	<i>This Instrument was developed by the NCI/CRCHD</i> Suggest including relevant demographic and population characteristic questions.

HPV Knowledge (Pre-Educational Activity)

Please answer each of the items below as True or False:

12) HPV is common.	<input type="checkbox"/> True	<input type="checkbox"/> False
13) HPV always has visible signs or symptoms.	<input type="checkbox"/> True	<input type="checkbox"/> False
14) HPV can cause cervical cancer (and other kinds of cancer).	<input type="checkbox"/> True	<input type="checkbox"/> False
15) HPV can be passed on by intimate skin-to-skin contact.	<input type="checkbox"/> True	<input type="checkbox"/> False
16) There are many types of HPV.	<input type="checkbox"/> True	<input type="checkbox"/> False
17) HPV can be passed on during sexual intercourse.	<input type="checkbox"/> True	<input type="checkbox"/> False
18) HPV can cause genital warts.	<input type="checkbox"/> True	<input type="checkbox"/> False
19) Men cannot get HPV.	<input type="checkbox"/> True	<input type="checkbox"/> False
20) HPV can be cured with antibiotics.	<input type="checkbox"/> True	<input type="checkbox"/> False
21) HPV usually doesn't need any treatment.	<input type="checkbox"/> True	<input type="checkbox"/> False
22) Most sexually active people will get HPV at some point in their lives.	<input type="checkbox"/> True	<input type="checkbox"/> False
23) A person could have HPV for many years without knowing it.	<input type="checkbox"/> True	<input type="checkbox"/> False
24) The HPV vaccine usually requires two doses.	<input type="checkbox"/> True	<input type="checkbox"/> False
25) The HPV vaccine offers protection against all sexually transmitted infections.	<input type="checkbox"/> True	<input type="checkbox"/> False
26) The HPV vaccine works best if given to people who have never had sex.	<input type="checkbox"/> True	<input type="checkbox"/> False
27) Someone who has had HPV vaccine cannot develop cervical cancer.	<input type="checkbox"/> True	<input type="checkbox"/> False
28) The optimal age for getting the HPV vaccine is 11-12 years of age.	<input type="checkbox"/> True	<input type="checkbox"/> False
29) The HPV vaccine is recommended for both boys and girls.	<input type="checkbox"/> True	<input type="checkbox"/> False
30) An HPV test can be done at the same time as a Pap test.	<input type="checkbox"/> True	<input type="checkbox"/> False

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Intentions

For each of the following statements, select the response choice that best applies to you.

Please tell us how strongly you agree or disagree with the following statements:	Strongly Agree	Agree	Unsure	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
1) I am likely to have my children vaccinated against HPV.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
2) I am likely to speak with my children's doctor about the HPV vaccine.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
3) I will talk to family members and friends about the HPV vaccine.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
4) I am likely to talk to my doctor about the HPV vaccine.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
5) I am likely to get the HPV vaccine.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

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Colorectal Cancer (CRC) Knowledge: Supplemental Materials (NCI)	
Intended respondents	Community members in the catchment area who are engaged.
Suggested periodicity	Administer alongside outreach activities.
Other notes for users	<i>This Instrument was developed by the NCI/CRCHD</i> Suggestion to include relevant demographic and population characteristic questions.

Pre-Educational Activity

For each of the following items, select the answer that you believe is correct.

- | | | | | | |
|---|------------------------------------|--|--|---|---|
| 1) Colorectal cancer starts in what part of the body? | <input type="checkbox"/> Liver | <input type="checkbox"/> Stomach | <input type="checkbox"/> Small Intestine | <input type="checkbox"/> Colon and/or rectum | |
| 2) A stool test (FIT/FOBT) checks your stool (poop) for? | <input type="checkbox"/> Blood | <input type="checkbox"/> Fat | <input type="checkbox"/> Tumors | <input type="checkbox"/> Polyps | |
| 3) Which of the following are risk factors for colorectal cancer?
<i>Please check all that are correct.</i> | <input type="checkbox"/> Poor diet | <input type="checkbox"/> Smoking/tobacco use | <input type="checkbox"/> Lack of physical activity | <input type="checkbox"/> Heavy drinking (alcohol consumption) | <input type="checkbox"/> Overweight/obesity |
| 4) In general, a colonoscopy should be performed every 10 years starting at age: | <input type="checkbox"/> 30 | <input type="checkbox"/> 40 | <input type="checkbox"/> 50 | <input type="checkbox"/> 60 | |
| 5) In general, a stool (poop) test (FIT or FOBT) should be done every year starting at age: | <input type="checkbox"/> 30 | <input type="checkbox"/> 40 | <input type="checkbox"/> 50 | <input type="checkbox"/> 60 | |
| 6) Lynch Syndrome is a disorder that runs in families and increases my chances of developing colorectal cancer. | <input type="checkbox"/> True | <input type="checkbox"/> False | | | |
| 7) The earlier that colorectal cancer is found, the greater my chances of survival. | <input type="checkbox"/> True | <input type="checkbox"/> False | | | |
| 8) Even if I have NO symptoms, I may still have colorectal cancer. | <input type="checkbox"/> True | <input type="checkbox"/> False | | | |
| 9) Polyps are growths in the lining of the colon or rectum that can develop into colorectal cancer. | <input type="checkbox"/> True | <input type="checkbox"/> False | | | |
| 10) A colonoscopy can be used to find polyps in the colon and rectum. | <input type="checkbox"/> True | <input type="checkbox"/> False | | | |

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11) A diet high in red meats and processed meats (lunch meat, hot dogs) increases my chances of developing colorectal cancer.	<input type="checkbox"/> True	<input type="checkbox"/> False
12) It is ok to skip colorectal cancer screening if I do not have any symptoms.	<input type="checkbox"/> True	<input type="checkbox"/> False
13) My chances of developing colorectal cancer are higher if someone in my immediate family has it or has had it.	<input type="checkbox"/> True	<input type="checkbox"/> False
14) Increasing my physical activity will NOT lower my chances of developing colorectal cancer.	<input type="checkbox"/> True	<input type="checkbox"/> False

Intentions

For each of the following statements, select the response choice that best applies to you.

Please tell us how strongly you agree or disagree with the following statements:	Strongly Agree	Agree	Unsure	Disagree	Strongly Disagree
I am likely to talk to a healthcare provider about colorectal cancer screening.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I am likely to get screened for colorectal cancer.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I am likely to talk about colorectal cancer with family members or friends.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I am likely to eat healthier.	<input type="checkbox"/>				
I am likely to increase my physical activity.	<input type="checkbox"/>				

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Appendix B: Evaluation Tracking Templates

Items included in this appendix are suggested for use if they align with your CPACHE sites activities. Any items labeled “Tracking Template” can be adopted by sites to assist with data collection for aggregation.

Cancer Related Resources (Tracking Item)	
Definition	Types of cancer related resources available through CPACHE programming.
Intended respondents	Outreach team member/One response per site
Suggested periodicity	Based on individual site needs
Other notes for users	This should only be used as a tracking item where the evaluator would aggregate the submissions.

1. CPACHE partnership:

(Please name your specific CPACHE institution, do not use acronyms)

- a. Cancer Center (CC) _____
- b. Institution serving underserved health disparity populations and underrepresented students (ISUPS)

Please indicate your role:

- a. Community member
- b. Investigator
- c. Service provider

2. Please indicate the types of community services that your center provides.

A. Webinars- Specify topics _____

Frequency: Monthly, Quarterly, Annually, ad hoc

B. On-site community training

Specify speaker expertise:

- Researcher
 - Specify topic _____
- Clinician
 - Specify topic _____

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- Community Advocate
 - Specify topic _____
- Cancer Survivor
 - Specify topic _____
- Other _____
 - Specify topic _____

Specify audience (ability to select more than one)

- Researchers
- Clinicians
- Community members
- Cancer Survivors
- Others _____

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Community Engagement: Tracking Item	
Definition	Bi-directional communication in cancer research topic identification, shared decision making and trust building and new partnership development.
Intended respondents	Core PIs or CPACHE funded research project investigators
Suggested periodicity	Annually
Other notes for users	None

U54 Community Engagement. *This includes cancer related assistance or consultation (technical or other) provided to a community.*

8. Who provided or conducted the assistance/consultation?

- a. MPI (contact PI)
- b. Administrative Core
- c. Planning and Evaluation Core
- d. Outreach Core
- e. Research Education Core
- f. Funded project lead (pilot/full)
- g. Shared Resource (lead)
- h. Other (please describe) _____

Month & Year	Assistance/consultation provided (<i>describe objective</i>)	Community, group, or organization to whom the assistance/ consultation was provided	What is the impact on the community?